

USE OF PRESUPPOSITION IN LINGUISTICS

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Abstract: *This article focuses on the study of the phenomenon of linguistic presupposition. The theoretical foundations of the phenomenon of presupposition, which is, part of pragmatics are considered.*

Key words: *pragmatics, presupposition, speech situation, secret judgment.*

Аннотация: *Данная статья посвящена исследованию феномена языковой пресуппозиции. Рассмотрены теоретические основы феномена пресуппозиции, являющейся частью прагматики.*

Ключевые слова: *прагматика, пресуппозиция, речевая ситуация, тайное суждение.*

Annotatsiya: *Ushbu maqola lingvistik pressuppozitsiya fenomenini o'rganishga qaratilgan. Pragmatikaning bir qismi bo'lgan pressuppozitsiya hodisasining nazariy asoslari ko'rib chiqiladi.*

Kalit so'zlar: *pragmatika, pressuppozitsiya, nutqiy vaziyat, yashirin hukm.*

Presuppositional aspect in linguistics is a concept that deals with the underlying assumptions or beliefs that are inherent in the meaning of a sentence or statement. It is an important aspect of language that is often overlooked, yet it plays a vital role in communication. It is a linguistic concept that plays a crucial role in the way we communicate. Presupposition refers to the underlying assumptions or beliefs that we hold about the world, which are often taken for granted in our

conversations. These assumptions can be expressed in a variety of ways, from the use of certain words or phrases to the structure of our sentences.

In this article, we will explore what presuppositions are, how they are formed, and their significance in different linguistic contexts. Presupposition is an important aspect of linguistics that concerns the assumptions that speakers make about the knowledge and beliefs of their audience. In other words, presuppositions are implicit assumptions that are conveyed through language and are typically taken for granted by both the speaker and the listener. For example, the sentence "John stopped smoking" presupposes that John used to smoke at some point in the past. The presupposition is not explicitly stated in the sentence, but it is implied. Similarly, the sentence "I'm sorry, but I can't lend you any money" presupposes that the speaker has been asked for money and that the person asking is in need of it.

Presuppositions can also be triggered by certain linguistic expressions, such as negation, questions, and definite descriptions. For instance, the sentence "I didn't steal your phone" presupposes that the listener believes their phone has been stolen, while the sentence "Do you still have that book I lent you?" presupposes that the speaker has previously lent a book to the listener. Understanding presuppositions is crucial for effective communication, as it allows speakers to convey information more efficiently and accurately. It also helps listeners to infer information that may not be explicitly stated, allowing them to better understand the speaker's intended meaning.

Presuppositions are implicit assumptions that are taken for granted in any given communication. They are not explicitly stated in the sentence, but they are present in the background knowledge of the speaker and the listener. For example, consider the sentence "John stopped smoking." The presupposition in this sentence is that John was smoking at some point in the past. The sentence cannot be true or false unless the presupposition is true.

Presuppositions are formed in different ways. One way is through lexical semantics, which refers to the meaning of individual words. For instance, the word "again" presupposes that an action has occurred before. Another way is through syntactic structures, which refer to the way words are organized into sentences. For example, the sentence "I regret eating the pizza" presupposes that the speaker ate the pizza.

Presuppositions are significant in different linguistic contexts, including pragmatics, semantics, and discourse analysis. In pragmatics, presuppositions are used to convey indirect meanings or implications. For example, the sentence "Do you still beat your wife?" presupposes that the listener has beaten his wife before, even if this is not true. In semantics, presuppositions are used to establish the truth conditions of a sentence. For instance, the sentence "The king of France is bald" presupposes that there is a king of France, even though there is none at present.

In discourse analysis, presuppositions are used to analyze the coherence and cohesion of a text. They help to identify the background knowledge that is shared between the speaker and the listener. For example, in a conversation about a movie, the presupposition might be that the listener has watched the movie before. Presuppositional aspect in linguistics has practical applications in language teaching, translation, and interpretation. Language teachers can use presuppositions to teach students how to infer meaning from context. Translators and interpreters can use presuppositions to produce accurate translations and interpretations that convey the intended meaning.

One aspect of presupposition is that it is often implicit rather than explicit. Speakers may make assumptions about what their audience knows or believes without ever explicitly stating those assumptions. For example, a speaker may say "I'm going to the store" without explicitly stating that they assume that their audience knows what a store is and where it is located.

Another aspect of presupposition is that it can be triggered by certain linguistic

cues. For example, the word "again" presupposes that something has happened before. If a speaker says "I'm going to watch the movie again", this presupposes that the speaker has already watched the movie at least once before.

Presupposition can also be used to convey information indirectly. For example, a speaker may say "Have you stopped beating your wife?" as a way of implying that the listener has beaten their wife in the past, even if the listener has never done so. This is an example of a presupposition that is conveyed indirectly through the choice of words.

Finally, presupposition can be used to create humor or irony. For example, a speaker may say "I love being stuck in traffic" as a way of implying the opposite, that they actually hate being stuck in traffic. This creates a humorous effect by playing with the audience's assumptions and expectations.

In conclusion, presupposition is an important aspect of language that helps to convey meaning and create subtle nuances in communication. It is a complex concept that is triggered by certain linguistic cues and can be used to convey information indirectly, create humor, or convey underlying assumptions about the world.

In linguistics, presupposition is studied as a way to understand how language is used to convey meaning. It is closely related to the concept of inference, which is the process of drawing conclusions based on the information that is presented to us. Presupposition is different from inference, however, in that it involves assumptions that are already part of our knowledge base, rather than conclusions that we draw from new information.

One of the most common ways that presupposition is expressed in language is through the use of presupposition triggers. These are words or phrases that signal to the listener that a certain assumption is being made. For example, if someone says "I'm going to the store again," the presupposition trigger is the word "again," which implies that the speaker has already been to the store at least once before.

Another way that presupposition is expressed in language is through the structure of our sentences. For example, if someone says "The president's wife is pregnant," the presupposition is that the president is a man. This is because the sentence is structured in a way that assumes the gender of the president, even though it is not explicitly stated.

Presupposition is also closely related to the concept of implicature, which is the meaning that is conveyed indirectly through our language use. Implicatures are often based on assumptions about the listener's knowledge or beliefs, and they can be either conventional (based on shared knowledge) or conversational (based on the context of the conversation).

One of the key applications of presupposition in linguistics is in the study of pragmatics, which is the branch of linguistics that deals with the ways in which context affects meaning. By understanding how presuppositions are used in language, linguists can gain insights into how meaning is conveyed through the social and cultural contexts in which we communicate.

In conclusion, presuppositional aspect in linguistics is an important concept that deals with implicit assumptions that are present in any communication. It is significant in different linguistic contexts, including pragmatics, semantics, and discourse analysis. Understanding presuppositions can help us to communicate effectively and accurately in different languages and cultural contexts. Overall, the use of presupposition in linguistics is an important tool for understanding how language is used to convey meaning. By studying the underlying assumptions and beliefs that are implicit in our language use, linguists can gain a deeper understanding of the ways in which we communicate with one another, and how we make sense of the world around us.

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